

Hydrazinates of Metal Acetates

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Among the hydrazinates of metal salts, those of metal acetates and substituted acetates are least studied^{1,2}. However, there has been no effective attempt for any detailed physicochemical investigation and spectra-structure correlation of this type of complexes. It is therefore considered interesting to investigate the donor properties of hydrazine towards acetates of bivalent Mg, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Cd.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to $M(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$. Except the Mg^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes, all others are non-hygroscopic. Generally all of them are less soluble in organic solvents. This is only to be expected as most of them exist as polymers. The complexes behave as non-electrolytes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
		Metal	Hydrazine
$\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	White	11.55 (11.70)	31 10 (31 20)
$\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	Flesh	23.10 (23.19)	26 40 (27 00)
$\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	Rose	24.90 (24 50)	26.10 (26 56)
$\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	Light blue	23.60 (24.39)	26 31 (26.59)
$\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	Bluish green	25 67 (25 90)	25.60 (25.88)
$\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$	White	37.80 (38.10)	21.50 (21.74)

$\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ exhibits a magnetic moment of 6.00 B.M. which together with its flesh colour indicate a high-spin octahedral geometry. $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ registers a magnetic moment of 5.21 B.M. which suggests octahedral geometry³. $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ records a magnetic moment of 3.26 B.M. as expected for octahedral nickel(II)⁴. A magnetic moment of 1.73 B.M. for $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ is consistent with the octahedral or distorted octahedral geometry. The Mg^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

All the complexes register a few uv bands at 200–360 nm due to ligand transitions. As a typical high-spin octahedral complex, $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ does not register any characteristic bands in its reflectance spectrum in the region 400–1000 nm⁵. In the Co^{II} complex, the band at 500 nm

may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition, typical of octahedral geometry⁵. In $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2$, the bands at 1000, 740 and 390 nm can be assigned respectively to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions in an octahedral geometry⁵. In the Cu^{II} complex, a broad band at ~615 nm with distinct shoulders indicates its distorted octahedral structure⁵. The Mg^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes do not exhibit any characteristic band in this region.

Usually two, but sometimes three bands are observed above 3000 cm^{-1} (NH_2) in the ir spectra of all the hydrazinate complexes. These bands are $50\text{--}100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ lower than the bands observed in hydrazine. The observed frequency decrease is of the same order of magnitude as that found in the case of amine complexes⁶. The band due to δ_{HNH} is found at $\sim 1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A strong band at $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and another one at $\sim 1420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{COO}^-)$. The observed separation ($\Delta\nu = 190\text{ cm}^{-1}$) supports the unidentate behaviour of acetate⁷. The bands due to $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ observed in the range $950\text{--}980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the presence of bidentate bridging hydrazine^{8,9}. Hence all the complexes are polymeric in nature. The non-ligand bands of medium intensity at $700\text{--}650$ and $400\text{--}360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Hydrazine hydrate (99–100%) was used as received. The complexes were prepared by modifying the reported methods⁹.

(i) To an alcoholic solution of the metal acetate hydrate, excess of hydrazine hydrate was added slowly with constant stirring. The reactions were instantaneous and the mixture was stirred for a few minutes. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} .

(ii) To a mixture of alcoholic solution of ammonium acetate and hydrazine hydrate, an aqueous solution of the respective metal chloride was added slowly with constant stirring. The Cd^{II} complex precipitated instantaneously. However, the Mg^{II} complex was isolated by complete evaporation of the reaction mixture under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} .

The complexes were characterised by analysis¹⁰, conductance ($\sim 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ in DMSO), magnetic moment (at $28 \pm 2^\circ$), reflectance and ir (KBr) spectral data.

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